

Fluorimetric Determination of Trace Amount of Nitrogen Dioxide

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A simple, rapid and selective fluorimetric method using acridine orange for determination of 0.4–5.0 ppm nitrate has been described. Effects of various parameters, like sulphuric acid concentration, reaction time, temperature, foreign species *etc.* have been discussed. The method has been used for the determination of nitrogen dioxide in air samples of Durgapur industrial area (Burdwan District).

THE analysis of atmospheric nitrogen dioxide is based on the conversion of nitrogen dioxide to nitrite or nitrate ion in a suitable absorbing medium for subsequent analysis. The most traditional method for the measurement of atmospheric levels of nitrogen dioxide was described by Jacobs and Hochheiser¹. Moreover, the Griess type reagents have also been used for the determination of atmospheric nitrogen dioxide by spectrophotometric methods^{2–5}. But the instability of coupling reagents is the main drawback of those methods. Several spectrophotometric methods for analysis of nitrate have been reported earlier^{6–11}. A number of reagents have been used for the determination of nitrite by fluorimetric methods^{12–14}, and for determination of nitrogen dioxide, 5-aminofluorescein¹⁴ has been used. Fluorimetric analysis of nitrate has been reported by several authors^{15,16}. Fluorescein¹⁷ has been used as a reagent for fluorimetric analysis of nitrate whereby the quenching of fluorescence intensity of the reagent was studied. In the present method, acridine orange has been used as a fluorimetric reagent for the analysis of nitrate and the quenching effect of the fluorescence intensity of the reagent has been studied. This rapid, simple fluorimetric method permits selective determination of nitrate in presence of 21 diverse species including those constituents which interfered in earlier method¹⁷. In the present method, the concentration of sulphuric acid used is lower and the sensitivity is higher than in the previous method¹⁷ based on fluorescence quenching.

Experimental

Fluorescence measurements were made with a Perkin-Elmer MPF 448 spectrophotometer. Quartz cell (1 cm) was used for all the analyses. Midget impingers of 35 ml capacity were used for air sampling and calibrated rotameters used for measuring the air-flow rate.

A standard nitrate solution ($6.4 \times 10^{-3} M$) was prepared by potassium nitrate (AnalaR) in 75%

sulphuric acid solution. Acridine orange (Hopkin and Williams) was used to prepare a $1.02 \times 10^{-5} M$ stock solution in 75% sulphuric acid solution. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. All aqueous solution were made using double-distilled water.

Procedure: A $5.1 \times 10^{-5} M$ acridine orange solution (0.3 ml) in 75% sulphuric acid and various amounts of nitrate (0–80 μg) in 75% sulphuric acid were taken in a small conical flask and allowed to stand on a water-bath ($\sim 80^\circ$) for 20 min. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and quantitatively transferred in a 10 ml volumetric flask. The resulting mixture was diluted to the mark with 75% sulphuric acid. The fluorescence intensity of the final solution was measured at 480 nm when it was excited at 352 nm.

Results and Discussion

Fluorescence characteristics and nature of the reaction product: The fluorescence intensity of acridine orange was checked under various media. It was found that the fluorescence of acridine orange was very strong in concentrated sulphuric acid medium and it decreased with the dilution of the acid medium. The excitation wavelengths of acridine orange were at 352 and 261 nm. The emission maximum was observed at 480 nm. It was also noted that the fluorescence intensity was greater when the sample was excited at 352 nm. The reaction product does not have any fluorescence. As a result, due to increase of the nitrate ion in the reaction mixture the fluorescence intensity of acridine orange decreases (Fig. 1).

Working curve: Working curve was prepared by the standard procedure. A typical working curve for $5.1 \times 10^{-5} M$ acridine orange reacting with nitrate in 75% sulphuric acid indicates that the amount of nitrate that could be estimated is in the range 0.4–5.0 ppm.

Effect of sulphuric acid concentration: The reaction between acridine orange and nitrate ion

Fig. 1. Emission spectra of acridine orange excited at 352 nm, $[\text{NO}_3^-]$: (A) 0.00, (B) 1.25, (C) 2.00, (D) 3.00, and (E) 4.25 ppm.

was strongly dependent upon the concentration of sulphuric acid. The reaction was carried out at different concentration of sulphuric acid. The quenching of fluorescence intensity of acridine orange by nitrate was studied. At and above 75% sulphuric acid, the quenching of fluorescence intensity was nearly the same. So this medium was chosen for the experiment.

Effect of reaction time and temperature : The reaction between nitrate and acridine orange in specified sulphuric acid medium was slow, taking 60 min to complete the reaction. Reaction time could be reduced to 20 min by heating the samples in a water-bath at $\sim 80^\circ$. At specified acidity, while the fluorescence intensity of acridine orange does not vary with temperature, its quenching by nitrate depends upon temperature.

Effect of foreign species : The interferences of foreign species were checked by combining them with nitrate solution and analysis being carried out by the standard procedure. A 100-fold molar excess of sulphur dioxide, acetate, hydrogen sulphide, phosphate caused no interference. The metal ions Ag^+ , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Sb^{3+} and Zn^{2+} did not interfere upto 100-fold more concentrated than nitrate ion. A 200-fold molar excess of acetone, formaldehyde, tartarate, EDTA and urea had no effect on the analysis. The interferences of chloride, bromide, iodide were removed by adding Sb^{3+} , and that due to nitrite was eliminated by using urea¹⁰.

Precision and accuracy : The confidence limit (95%) interval for 4 determinations at 1.95 ppm of nitrate was ± 0.07 ppm. The relative standard deviation was $\pm 1.5\%$.

Air sampling and its treatment : The present method was applied for the analysis of nitrogen dioxide in air samples at three stations of Durgapur industrial area in the district of Burdwan. Air samples were drawn through bubblers at a flow-rate of $0.45 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The two bubblers were connected in series. A 0.7 N triethanolamine absorbing solution (10 ml) was taken in each bubbler¹⁰. At regular intervals the air samples were collected for about three months. The nitrogen dioxide was converted into a mixture of nitrite and

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF NITROGEN DIOXIDE IN AIR

Location	Sample No	Volume of air dm^3	NO_2 in air ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)		Relative average deviation %
			Present method	Standard method	
I	1	155.14	37.30	37.06	0.32
	2	143.21	53.88	54.40	0.48
	3	142.98	41.52	40.82	0.85
	4	169.00	43.90	44.95	1.18
	5	170.06	43.64	43.20	0.51
	6	167.50	33.66	33.70	0.06
II	1	120.36	65.95	66.02	0.05
	2	170.28	57.51	57.25	0.23
	3	168.70	44.85	45.65	0.88
	4	144.60	71.83	71.57	0.18
	5	143.21	64.76	64.55	0.16
	6	145.10	51.13	50.62	0.50
III	1	146.30	50.74	49.20	1.54
	2	171.53	51.91	52.17	0.25
	3	131.55	61.00	60.40	0.49
	4	122.68	64.70	65.20	0.38
	5	170.40	82.72	81.85	0.53

nitrate in the basic absorbing medium. The absorbing solutions of the two bubblers were mixed after sampling and was made acidic with dilute sulphuric acid. The nitrite present was oxidised to nitrate by using 10 volume hydrogen peroxide²⁰ (2 ml) and the excess peroxide was destroyed by boiling for 15 min. Finally, the volume was reduced to 2-3 ml. A solution of the residue was made in 75% sulphuric acid and taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask and then diluted to the mark with 75% sulphuric acid. An aliquot (5 ml) was taken and analysed by the present method. Another portion of the sample was analysed by standard method²¹ for comparison. Results are presented in Table 1.

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